

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING: A TRANSDISCIPLINARY APPROACH

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Abstract :

Today in the world of globalization, in this age of digitization, teaching of English language has become challenging one. As defined by the academia, ELT has been considered as a research discipline under the field of 'applied linguistics'. Teaching and learning English language and using it as an extra language is intricate and multifaceted. The process of English language teaching and learning involve languages, cultures, learning, communication, identities, etc., which in turn are placed educationally within a host of diverse disciplines. One can say that language teaching and learning is transdisciplinary as multiple disciplines can offer diverse lenses through which to understand the same phenomena and to build new understandings of the object of interest. Furthermore, as a field in which languages and cultures are inherently brought into contact, language teaching and learning is also at an intersection between disciplines that are conceptualized and developed differently in different languages and academic traditions. The present research paper will examine how language teaching and learning is adopting a transdisciplinary perspective in today's changing world. In particular, it will focus on the idea of language learning from an intercultural perspective to examine how multiple disciplines and different disciplinary traditions contribute to shaping understanding of the field; it will also consider some of the challenges of bringing multiple disciplines to bear on this understanding.

Key words: *Academic, research, cultures and traditions, language teaching and learning, applied linguistics, transdisciplinary*

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Introduction :

‘What innovative I can explore for my students?’ thinks an enthusiastic mind of English language teacher. Indeed, today in the world of globalization, in this age of digitization, teaching of English language has become challenging one. As defined by the academia, ELT has been considered as a research discipline under the field of ‘applied linguistics’. Teaching and learning English language and using it as an extra language is intricate and multifaceted. The

process of English language teaching and learning involve languages, cultures, learning, communication, identities, etc., which in turn are placed educationally within a host of diverse disciplines. One can say that language teaching and learning is transdisciplinary as multiple disciplines can offer diverse lenses through which to understand the same phenomena and to build new understandings of the object of interest. Furthermore, as a field in which languages and cultures are inherently brought into contact, language teaching and learning is also at an intersection between disciplines that are conceptualized and developed differently in different languages and academic traditions. This analysis paper can examine however instruction and learning is adopting a transdisciplinary perspective in today's ever-changing world. Especially, it'll specialize in the concept of learning from an intercultural perspective to look at however multiple disciplines and totally different disciplinary traditions contribute to shaping understanding of the field; it'll additionally think about a number of the challenges of transferal multiple disciplines in reality on this understanding. Before having, the in-depth understanding transdisciplinary approach to the English language teaching and learning, it would be significant for us to commence with the question 'What does it mean by transdisciplinary?' When we talk about English language teaching and learning as a central focus of applied linguistics, we delimit it to just a discipline or sub-discipline of applied linguistics. To speak broadly, English language teaching and learning is an area of investigation that is understood and researched from many disciplinary and sub-disciplinary. This disciplinary plurality has been long recognized by the linguists, scholars and academicians. Savignon (1991) argued that Communicative Language Teaching "can be seen to derive from a multidisciplinary perspective that includes, at least, linguistics, psychology, philosophy, sociology, and educational research" (265).

However, we should be aware here that the issue a teacher faces during the language teaching and learning is not simply one of a collective *multidisciplinary* but it is the issue that requires a *synthesizing* of approach to understand the phenomenon plurality and that crosses a disciplinary boundary. It is called as '*transdisciplinarity*', an approach which is between, across and beyond disciplines. Cambridge online dictionary define the term transdisciplinarity as the approach that involving or relating to two or more different areas of study. There are some of the issues involved in the development of transdisciplinarity in language teaching and learning.

Transdisciplinarity approach can be understood as an interactive approach between disciplines in the form of a dialogue between specialists in particular paradigms to create multidimensional responses to understanding the complexity of phenomena. Transdisciplinarity approach to English language teaching and learning involves the incorporation of perceptions from diverse disciplines into the field of ELT, although this conceptualization is less developed yet. Language teaching and language learning have always been seen as complex, complicated and multi-layered field as it involves culturally context meanings, pragmatics of meaning, psychological aspects, multimodality, sociolinguistic variability, etc. and ultimately requiring not just the ability to make meaning but also to understand the meaning-making process itself. English Language learning and teaching is thus not just language focused but requires teaching and learning that goes beyond language and a specific discipline. It requires engagement with theories of learning from outside Language acquisition.

To develop the expertise in English Language learning and teaching, the language educator or teacher should avoid his focus on only in one discipline or sub-discipline. He should enhance his expertise in other disciplines or sub-disciplines as well. A crossing of disciplinary and sub-disciplinary boundaries is the best approach a teacher can adopt. The focus of language education is not simply language; it is a confluence of language, culture, intercultural capabilities, learners, learning, teachers, pedagogy, curriculum, policy, etc. and different aspects of language teaching and learning require different theory, methods, and literatures.

Benefits of Transdisciplinary Approach :

With the Transdisciplinary approach, the educators can teach English language through the variety of perspectives. They can enable the learners to advance and upgrade their vital skills like LSRW skills, analytical skill, interpersonal skill, leadership skills, and communication skills that will encourage them to take responsibility for their learning as they ask questions to understand the world around them and discover topics that interest them.

By using the Transdisciplinary approach to English Language teaching, the educators enables learners to improve their concepts and skills across diverse subject areas, rather than studying subjects in isolation as we know that subjects are distinctive, but they are interrelated.

Transdisciplinary approach to English Language teaching allow the teachers to impart a holistic learning experience to the learners which they relate to a variety of contexts.

What Are Transdisciplinary Skills?

The following skills are to be considered as Transdisciplinary Skills that are classified into five categories:

1. **Thinking Skills:** It includes knowledge acquisition, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation
2. **Self-management Skills:** The self-management skills comprises gross motor skills, fine motor skills, organisation, time-management, safety, healthy lifestyle, codes of behaviour, informed choices
3. **Communication Skills:** It includes Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing, Viewing, Presenting, Non-verbal communication
4. **Social Skills:** Social Skills are important. These includes accepting responsibility, respecting others, cooperating, resolving conflict, group decision-making, adopting a variety of roles
5. **Research skills:** It comprises formulating questions, observing, planning, collecting, recording, organising and interpreting data

Gaining these transdisciplinary skills, learners will work independently and in groups of varying sizes and compositions. These skills will allow them to develop these sub-skills further as they encounter different viewpoints and analyse topics from a variety of angles.

Challenges in English Language Teaching :

There are host of challenges an educator, teacher faces. These can be enlisted as follows

- Disturbed Environment of the Class.

- Limited Teaching Resources.
- A Large Number of Students in the Classroom.
- Wrong Syllabus to be Teach.
- Limited Time for Lecture to Teach.
- Students Hijack Lessons.
- Students Disturbed the Class.
- Using Other Languages in the Classrooms.

However these challenges can be overcome by the teacher if he is receptive in facing them.

Conclusion :

Transdisciplinary approach to English Language teaching and learning has opened up a new door to the educator. It has to be exploited thoroughly. It can be useful in overall improvement of the students' language learning skills. Transdisciplinary approach can build up the confidence of the students as they would be acquainted to the variety of content and jargons.

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